

Analyses of GIS data were conducted in QGIS 3.4.1 (Maderia).

Projection: All layers were projected in the World Geodetic System 1984 (WGS 84) format. Specimen data were loaded in QGIS as a Delimited Text Layer, with latitude and longitude designated as X and Y-coordinates respectively, thereby treating each specimen as a data point.

Elevation Data: We extracted elevation values for each data point in QGIS using the 'Point Sampling Tool' plugin. Elevation values were then exported for statistical analysis using the MMQGIS Import/Export, Export Attribute Values as CSV function. For statistical analyses we gave specimens with slope measurements of 0 a small non-zero value (0.01).

Slope Estimate: To estimate slope, ratio of vertical to horizontal units was set to 111320 units (to correct for distance in degrees and elevation in meters), we again utilized the mean elevation rasters and estimated slope using the Raster -> Analysis -> Slope tool in QGIS.

Using the 'Point sampling tool' plugin, slope was extracted for each specimen and slopes were exported in the same way as elevation for further statistical analysis. For statistical analyses we gave specimens with slope measurements of 0 a small non-zero value (0.01).

Flow Estimate: To extract flow values, it was necessary to convert flow lines into vectorized point data (QGIS, Vector -> Geometry Tools -> Extract Vertices). Then form 0.0015° circle buffers around specimens (QGIS, Vector -> Geoprocessing Tools -> Buffer). Find the location of intersections (QGIS, Vector -> Geoprocessing Tools -> Intersect). Output resulting flow data. (QGIS, Vector -> Analysis Tools -> List Unique Values)